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***Shiva Trilogy* by Amish: A Subaltern Reading**

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Abstract:

The paper applies subaltern theory to analyse the marginalisation of weak and oppressed classes in society as described in the *Shiva Trilogy* which justifies the inclusion of the deprived. The Subalterns are the deprived masses of the world who are facing discrimination based on colour, creed, and caste. The rigid caste system in India and neighbouring countries has led Dalits to a hellish existence. Mythology-based literature narrates this phenomenon through fictitious stories. As a torch bearer of equality and justice, Shiva, the protagonist of Amish has a passion for inclusivity which leads to the assimilation of the subalterns into the mainstream. The paper attempts to highlight the place of the subalterns in the Meluhan kingdom of Sapt Sindhu in Amish's *Shiva Trilogy* and the necessity of their assimilation into society.

Keywords: Vikarma, assimilation, Naga, subalterns, inclusivity, inclusion.

Introduction

The subaltern studies have traces of Marxism, Post-Structuralism and postcolonial theory. It gained popularity along with globalisation and multiculturalism. The subalterns are the oppressed people of different origins and regions who are deprived and discriminated on account of baseless reasons. Amish has represented their case with empathy in his *Shiva Trilogy* where the protagonist realises his vision of an inclusive society by making the people of Sapt Sindhu work together in harmony without jingoism. Amish's idea of inclusivity is commendable as he voices his ideology through the hero of the *Shiva Trilogy*, whose bildungsroman transforms him into a Mahadev (god of the gods). The character of Shiva in the

text is not divine like Lord Shiva of Hinduism who is a deity, however, he becomes a Mahadev by performing noble deeds of fighting evil and changing laws in favour of the outcasts. Vikarma is the name given to people who are not allowed to marry or touch others as they may poison others with their bad fates. It is believed that Vikarma persons are punished in this birth for the sins committed in their previous birth and they must suffer with dignity in their present birth. Shiva sets an example by marrying Sati, a Vikarma, and gets the law against Vikarma people abolished. He also accepts Ganesh, the Naga child of Sati from her first marriage. Naga people are born with physical deformities so they are not allowed to live in Sapt Sindhu for their alliance with Chandravanshis and involvement in dreadful terrorist activities. Shiva accepts Kali the Naga sister of Sati and Ganesh as family members who were thrown at the time of birth due to physical outgrowths on their body. He condemns the practice of Vikarma according to which people were declared outcasts on the pretext of their misfortunes. Neelkanth, the saviour (Shiva) raises his voice against this practice and by making the law null and void, assimilates Vikarmas into the mainstream. Kumar (2014) appreciates Shiva's efforts by stating, "Shiva doesn't mind touching of the Vikarmas. During his visit to Kotdwaar, he steps forward and touches the feet of the blind man, a Vikarma, and seeks blessing from him. The whole crowd is spellbound as he openly breaks the Meluhan law. He resolves to demolish this social structure and comes out as a spokesman for the Vikarmas" (363). He again observes "He works as a link between privileged and non-privileged, between the king and the subjects. People of Meluha, Swadeep, Branga and Naga become his followers. These people sacrifice their duty (swadharma) for the greater cause- Universal Dharma" (364).

Shiva's efforts for social reformation without any selfish motive make him a successful leader. The people of Meluha, Swadeep, Branga, and Panchavati follow him in finding and destroying evil. The inclusion of immigrants in Meluha is also a prominent case due to their search for the Neelkanth. King Daksha of Meluha, the Suryavanshi Kingdom, invites people of different tribes by offering citizenship and other facilities for this selfish motive. Capt. Nandi lures Shiva, a tribal chieftain of the Guna tribe to migrate for the greener pastures. Capt. Nandi is a representative of Meluha and has come to this land to give Shiva's tribe, a chance of migrating to Meluha where a civilised and safe life awaits them. However, this privilege is given to the tribals for the ulterior motive of King Daksha who is waiting for the emergence of the Neelkanth. According to the legend, Neelkanth, the saviour will be from outside, and after consuming the Somras his neck will turn blue so the assimilation of immigrants into Meluhan society is not for the sake of immigrant welfare but for the discovery of the Saviour who will

lead them to victory against the evil Chandravanshis. On the other hand, the impartial behaviour of Shiva as a leader is highly laudable as he accords respect to every soldier by giving the slogan 'Har Har Mahadev' during the war against the evil Chandravanshis. It also endorses inclusion as Shiva encourages the soldiers to consider themselves 'Mahadevs' and show their gallantry. He explains to them that every soldier is a Mahadev as each one is fighting against evil. The admiration and regard expressed by the leader to all the soldiers irrespective of their status lead them to victory. The exemplary courage makes Shiva a living God who does not discriminate between royals/nobles and common citizens.

Shiva's kindness in granting permission for making a Vikarma Brigade during the war gives unprecedented honour and significance to Vikarmas who were enduring punishments by the society for the baseless superstitions of contamination by touch. Even the Chandravanshis are absorbed by Shiva, who does not consider them evil as he finds them only different in principles. Suryavanshis believe in Truth, duty, and honour, and Chandravanshis believe in passion, beauty, and freedom. Shiva thinks of the welfare of society in the long run when knowledge of Somras might become useful. After the victory, he does not take revenge but works for a peaceful multicultural society where Suryavanshis, Chandravanshis, Brangas, and Nagas can live together without malice and discrimination. The paper examines the texts through the lens of subaltern studies.

Literature Survey

Subaltern theory describes the 'Other' as the one who is oppressed on account of caste, race, class or gender. The prominent proponents of this theory were Ranjit Guha and Gayatri Chakravarti Spivak who promoted the 'voice' of the deprived. Marginalisation and discrimination affect people socially, economically, politically, and legally. Sen, Amartya (2005) in his book *The Argumentative Indian* exhorts "The right to comprehensive participation in democratic politics can be the basis of social and political use of 'voice' – through arguments and agitations- to advance the cause of equality in different spheres of life" (36). APJ Abdul Kalam (2015) also declares "Enriching the nation is not limited to simply economic terms but it also means enriching the nation with knowledge, with sweat and above all, with honour and dignity" (28). Indian society carries the burden of discrimination based on caste which Amish has described by concepts of Vikarma and Nagas in the Suryavanshi kingdom, Meluha, where the dominant class oppresses the subservient class. The ideology of the Meluhan society separates the weak from the strong and makes way for segregation and accumulation of power

structure. By opposing this system, Shiva unites people of different regions of Sapt Sindhu and Nagas for a common cause of fighting evil, thereby setting a praiseworthy example of social inclusion. The vicious circle of discrimination prevents people from participating in normal life which leads to their further isolation from the mainstream. The Naga land is called Panchavati which is not accessible to people other than Nagas and their biological parents who want to live with the misfortunes of their children. The hero's greatness is proved when he changes the law against discrimination where separate rules for royals and the masses exist in the society. Basu (2020) argues that "Tripathi attempts at a vision of inclusivity, by his clever techniques of the representation of the disabled and the divine alike" (96).

The depiction of various classes and their access to resources and power in the *Trilogy* can be scrutinised by examining how economic and social inequalities are perpetuated or challenged within the story. The Exploitation of marginalised groups, particularly Vikarmas and the Nagas reflects present-day exploitations of subalterns. VijayKarthic and Immanuel (2018) state "The ideology of considering a being is inferior than another just based on the curse can be analogised with the present-day caste system. The Vikarmas are seen as inferior to other human beings and thus they are treated less than normal" (208). The belief in karma is religiously honoured by the Suryavanshis in Meluha, a near-perfect empire of the Sapt Sindhu. His uncle prophesied that Shiva's destiny would take him away from those massive mountains and his Karma would lead him to a better future turns out to be true. Shiva with the consent of his tribe decides to go along with Capt. Nandi to Meluha for a better, more peaceful life without unnecessary fights for the territory's safety. Their migration to Meluha lacks the pain and nostalgia generally suffered by the migrants. Although Meluhans call their kingdom perfect Shiva discovers many traditions baseless and inhuman especially the concept of Vikarma which reduces a person to a guilty and depressed soul who craves acceptance. Kumar (2017) appreciates Shiva "As a man Shiva brings social reformation in the totalitarian society of Meluha. His fulfilling harmonious and progressive life is lived in accordance with Dharma. He marries widowed Sati, and accepts Ganesh, born out of her first marriage, as his son" (400). The concept of 'Othering' is quite visible in the Meluhan society where a particular section of society is victimised because of their misfortunes in current life due to the belief in past life sins. As it is established that they are the carriers of bad fate and might contaminate other people's lives if they marry or touch others, they are segregated and forced to suffer with dignity. Even royal family members cannot participate in normal life if declared Vikarma. Princess Sati, the heroine of the *Trilogy* is a victim of this custom and is rescued by the

Neelkanth when he abolishes the law of Vikarma and encourages all Vikarmas to lead a normal life like other citizens.

Protagonist of Shiva Trilogy: A Subaltern Hero

Shiva's transformation from a humble tribal chief to a revered leader proves him a subaltern hero who challenges patriarchal norms and hierarchies in Meluhan society. Even Sati rises from the stigma of Vikarma to a warrior queen highlighting the struggles and resilience of subaltern women. Shiva is surprised to see the procession of Vikarma women. 'As they turned and walked into the lane.' Shiva asked, "Who are Vikarma women?"

Vikarma people, 'my lord' said Nandi sighing deeply "are people who have been punished in this birth for the sins of their previous birth. Hence, they have to live this life without dignity and tolerate their present sufferings with grace. This is the only way they can wipe their Karma and clean the sins of their previous birth. Vikarma men have their own order of penance and women have their own order." (*The Immortals of Meluha* 95)

Shiva revolts against this and marries widowed Sati after eradicating this law for one and all. Similarly, Nagas are hated and kept away from the Sapt Sindhu due to their hideous physical deformities. They are believed to have an alliance with the evil Chandravanshis. Nagas are introduced in the first book of the Trilogy: "They are cursed people, my lord... are born with hideous deformities because of their previous births. Deformities like extra hands or horribly misshapen faces. But they have tremendous strength and skills. The Naga name alone strikes terror in any citizen's heart. They are not even allowed in the Sapt Sindhu'...our land my lord, the land of seven rivers." (*The Immortals of Meluha*, 61).

Naga songs outpour their emotions:

You were my world,

My god, my

Creator;

And yet, you

abandoned me. (*The Secrets of the Nagas* 147)

Their queen Kali does not have faith in the theory of punishment for past life sins that exclude Nagas from society. She exhibits her discontent towards injustices and craves acceptance and recognition which she receives from Shiva after a dramatic turn of events. As the twin sister of Sati, with outgrowths on her body, she was abandoned at the time of her birth by King Daksha, her father, to save family honour and political power. Ganesh was also abandoned without his mother's knowledge for the same reasons. Their physical deformities classified them as cursed people who should stay away from their families in Meluha. These stigmatised and peripheral beings are forced to live in Panchavati, a place away from the so-called civilised Meluhan Empire. Their goodness is proven many times over but people, in general, consider them evil and inauspicious due to their physical abnormalities. Nagas provide medicine to Branga people who suffer due to the consumption of water polluted by the intoxicants released in the river after the manufacturing of the Somras. Sati is also saved during her pregnancy by the medicines supplied to her secretly by the efforts of Ganesh. There is also an incident when Ganesh almost receives fatal injuries while saving a common woman from a crocodile despite Nagas' courage and helping nature, they are feared by everyone as their outgrowths and misshapen faces make them look hideous. Along with Shiva Sati also exhibits compassion and happily supports her Naga sibling, Kali, and son Ganesh.

Shiva brings harmony and peace not only by assimilating Vikarma and Nagas but also by people from other walks of life who live on the periphery of the mainstream. He tames a dreaded bandit Parshuram who lives with other bandits in the Jungle and helps the Branga people in procuring medicine from the Nagas. Shiva is flabbergasted when Parshuram reveals quite contradictory perceptions about the Nagas, "They never kill innocents. They fight for justice; despite the injustices they endure. They help the oppressed whenever and wherever they can. They truly are the best amongst us all." (*The Secret of the Nagas* 268)

This outlaw believes in the legend of the Neelkanth, so he surrenders unconditionally to Shiva who makes him part of the army that fights against the evil of Somras led by Shiva himself. Shiva's psychoanalytic understanding makes Parshuram divulge the secrets of his personal life which had led him to grow into an outlaw. Shunned by the society he lived with his followers and was considered invincible. Shiva exposes many such fissures within the perfect empire of the Meluhan social structure.

The compassion of Shiva for the beggar at the Ramjanambhoomi temple, whose kindness opens the door of dignity for the poor, is just the opposite of the masculine society of

Meluha. Shiva's acceptance of food forced by the beggar makes Shiva realize that Chandravanshis are not entirely evil. Their lifestyle is different from the Suryavanshis' code of conduct. "Freedom. Freedom for the wretched to also have dignity. Something impossible in Meluha's system of governance." (*The Immortals of Meluha* 389)

Segregation of normal and abnormal based on superstition and physical deformities is a part of the Meluhan society. The advent of power also changes truth according to the rulers' perspective. People in power decide what is right, what is normal, and what truth is, so with the change in power, the definition of truth and normalcy also changes. When King Daksha rules, he follows old traditions of Vikarma by excluding Nagas from his kingdom but when Shiva, the Neelkanth appears and his supremacy is established, acceptance and inclusion of Nagas and Vikarmas becomes a new normal for the society at large. New power celebrates equality and inclusivity unlike the old power structure and victimisation of Vikarmas and Nagas which was once acceptable becomes hateful and disagreeable. Meluhan society also has strong and weak sections based on power. Nagas also have beak-like noses, extra hands, and abnormal outgrowths on their bodies which make them different from normal human beings. They are also considered monsters by Meluhan society. Gopal, the chief of Vasudev clarifies "The Nagas are feared and cursed as demons. Many millennia ago, they were respected. After winning this war they will become respectable and powerful once again as loyal allies of the Neelkanth" (*The Oath of the Vayuputras* 206)

The caste system of Meluha and its justification can be seen in their Maika system. The hospital city called Maika in Meluha is a unique way to provide equal opportunities to all the children born to Meluhan parents. Parvateshwar justifies Meluhan social setup:

As we agreed, the best society is the one where a person's caste is decided purely by his abilities and Karma. Lord Ram created a practical system that ensured this. All children that are born in Meluha are compulsorily adopted by the empire. To ensure that this is done methodically, a great hospital city called Maika was built deep in the South. All pregnant women must travel there for their delivery. Only pregnant women are allowed into the city, nobody else (*The Immortals of Meluha* 99).

Since time immemorial lower classes have been suffering from discrimination based on the caste system. The elite or the so-called higher class has subjugated depressed classes for its personal and political gain. Despite talent and knowledge, mythical characters like Karna, Eklavya, and Shambook were ill-treated by the oppressive elites. Social inequalities have

always been a part of the Indian social construct and the vision of inclusivity which is also part of our culture is highlighted by Amish in *the Shiva Trilogy* by the amalgamation of Vikarmas, Nagas, Chandravanshis, and Brangas who were otherwise considered evil people by the Suryavanshis.

Conclusion

The necessity of inclusion is a noble aim projected by Amish in many of his books like the *Shiva Trilogy*. Here the protagonist prevents the exploitation and expropriation of subalterns and saves them from deprivation and degradation. The hegemonic oppression of King Daksha represents fundamental erasures and exclusions based on the superstitions of past life sins. The trilogy explores the intrusion of the mainstream into the mental and physical geography of the margins. Amish's subaltern concern informs, rebels, and incorporates victims in the army and other spheres of life. He weaves a blueprint for repositioning his narrative by empowering the marginalised and the deprived. He also exhorts us to sacrifice *swadharma* (personal faith) for universal dharma (faith applicable to the whole of humanity) for the greater good, championing the dictum of 'Atmano Mokshartham Jagat Hitaye' (My salvation is tied to the salvation of all the beings of the universe). This necessity of inclusion of disadvantaged groups in contemporary society is highly justified as a social hierarchy has poisoned the spirit of equality. Coexistence is the hallmark of this era of hyper-globalization in a world that is a heterogeneous melting pot of cultures, ultimately conflating into an all-embracing wholeness. The multicultural world awaits enlightened individuals who can brighten the flame of equality and fraternity for a more civilised society.

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